

Article

The Geometric Meaning of Traditional Inertial Frames According to Neutrosophical Logic

Ranim Fajer ¹, Mountajab Al-Hasan ^{2,*} and Monir Makhlof ³

¹Assistant Professor of Mathematics, Albaath University, Homs, Syria; ranimfajer6@gmail.com

²Professor of Mathematics, Albaath University, Homs, Syria; alhasanmountajab@gmail.com

³Professor of Mathematics, Albaath University, Homs, Syria; Monirmaklohf@albaath-univ.edu.sy

*Correspondence: alhasanmountajab@gmail.com

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Abstract: In paper, from the view of neutrosophic logic we study the concept of inertial reference frames. First, we study the Galilean structure, and specifically discussed the concepts of two simultaneous events and two events occurring at the same place. We also study the various reference frames that allow to represent the coordinates of events in Galilean space. We also show that the set of inertial transformations are a ten-dimensional neutrosophic group, which is the same usual one, but we provide a neutrosophic geometric way to derive them.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Logic, Galilean Structure and Space, Inertial Frames, Galilean Transformations, Classical Mechanics.

1. Introduction

Ptolemy built the first integrated model of the universe (considering the Earth to be an absolutely static sphere (the center of the universe). He also considered that all celestial bodies without exception revolve around our earth and our friend the sun revolving resoundingly around this center[1].

Ptolemy's model was very influential (the stillness of the earth in the static state is very self-evident (and its centrality is a logical consequence of its static stillness (this model has become part of human thinking (intersected with most beliefs and became a sacred model.

This model did not convince Copernicus (who believed that the Earth is not static (but that it and the rest of the known planets revolve around the Sun (but was forced to say the opposite[2]. Bruno went further (saying that the Earth revolves around the sun (that the sun is only a star like other stars (that there may be distant planets orbiting another star (and that there may be life elsewhere than Earth. Bruno gave his life as a price for his belief and did not back down[3].

Galilei (in turn (believed that the Earth revolves around the sun (but because of his invention of the astronomical binoculars (he was famous (and escaped execution[4].

Galilei introduced another concept to the static and dynamic problems and set (the principle of inertia (which states that each isolated body is stationary or moving in a uniform straight motion. This principle is true if we relate the position of the isolated body to a coherent comparison frame with the Sun (or any frame that moves with respect to the Sun in a uniform straight motion.

These frames are called Inertial frames or Galilean frames .Galilei's equivalence of the static solar frame with the other frames moving in a uniform straight motion, is based on the fact that the passenger in the belly of a ship moving in a straight and uniform motion cannot know that it is moving unless he climbs to the surface and sees its movement with his own eyes [5].

It was very clear that this definition could be reversed ‘since the frame in which the principle of inertia satisfied is an inertial frame .Newton generalized the principle of inertial by saying that the forces provide the moving body in a inertial frame with acceleration linearly with it by the relationship $\vec{F} = m\vec{a}$, that the isolated body has zero acceleration and its motion is straight and uniform [6].

In other hand, many theoretical and practical science are developed from the classical to neutrosophic logic; for example: the statistics; the probability; biology and other. In 2023 the neutrosophic logic was extend to include the geometrical sense [7-19]; that allow to study the geometrical point and to generalize the geometrical point to the material one [20]. In [20]; the position, velocity and acceleration vectors of the material point were discussed for the plane motion of the material point in the neutrosophic plane.

2. Materials and Methods (proposed work with more details)

In order to meet the requirements of this research ‘we need to introduce following new definitions:

2.1. Definition:(Neutrosophical affine space $\varepsilon(I)$ above the real Neutrosophical vector space $\mathbb{R}^n(I)$, of the n dimension):

Let $\varepsilon(I)$ be a set of Neutrosophical points and consider the neutrosophic real vector space $\mathbb{R}^n(I)$.

We call $\varepsilon(I)$ an neutrosophic affine space above the real neutrosophic vector space $\mathbb{R}^n(I)$, if and only if there is an application L of the from:

$$L: \varepsilon(I) \times \varepsilon(I) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n(I) \\ (A, B) \mapsto \overrightarrow{AB}$$

Achieves the following:

1)The relationship of Shawl in the Neutrosophical sense:

$$\forall A, B, C \in \varepsilon(I): \overrightarrow{AB} + \overrightarrow{BC} = \overrightarrow{AC}$$

2) one to one correspondence:

$$\forall O \in \varepsilon(I), \vec{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n(I); \exists p \in \varepsilon(I): \overrightarrow{Op} = \vec{u}$$

2.2 .The Definition of the neutrosophic Galilean Events Space $\varepsilon(I)$:

The neutrosophic Galilean event space $\varepsilon(I)$ ‘ is an neutrosophic affine space on the real neutrosophical vector space $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$,that there is an affine application:

$$L: \varepsilon(I) \times \varepsilon(I) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4(I) \\ (A, B) \mapsto \overrightarrow{AB}$$

Achieves the following:

1)The relationship of Shawl in the Neutrosophical sense:

$$\forall A, B, C \in \varepsilon(I): \overrightarrow{AB} + \overrightarrow{BC} = \overrightarrow{AC}$$

2) one to one correspondence:

$$\forall O \in \varepsilon(I), \vec{u} \in \mathbb{R}^4(I); \exists p \in \varepsilon(I): \overrightarrow{Op} = \vec{u}$$

We call each element of $\varepsilon(I)$ neutrosophic. The neutrosophic Galilean events ‘are all past ‘ present and future events ‘for examples: star explosion or pen touching paper‘ ... etc.

2.3. Elements of the Neutrosophical Galilean Structure (Time ‘Simultaneous Space ‘Scalar Product):

The Galilean structure from the point of view of neutrosophical logic is based on the concepts of neutrosophical time ‘and the neutrosophical simultaneous space ‘provided with a neutrosophical

scalar product, which allows us to measure the norms of simultaneous vectors and the angles between these vectors ‘without the possibility of measuring the norms of non-simultaneous vectors or calculating the angles between them.

2.3. A. Neutrosophical time:

The neutrosophical time from Galilea's point of view is an immersive linear function:

$$T: \mathbb{R}^4(I) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}(I)$$

Which attaches each vector from $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$ with a real neutrosophical number of $\mathbb{R}(I)$.

Let $A, B \in \varepsilon(I)$ be two events from the Galilean event space $\varepsilon(I)$, then the vector $\overrightarrow{AB}$ is a vector from $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$.

The neutrosophical real number $T(\overrightarrow{AB})$ represents the past time¹ from event A to event B . Here we distinguish the three cases:

If $T(\overrightarrow{AB}) = 0$, events A and B are simultaneous events.

If $T(\overrightarrow{AB}) > 0$, we said that event A occurred before event B .

If $T(\overrightarrow{AB}) < 0$, we said that event B occurred before event A .

Note.1 :The simultaneous of events forms an equivalence relationship defined on $\varepsilon(I)$. We call the equivalence classes of this relationship, a neutrosophical time moments. These neutrosophical moments in time form a partition of the Galilean Neutrosophical event space $\varepsilon(I)$.

2.3. B. Simultaneous space:

Since the linear time application T is immersive ‘so its kernel $E(I)$ is a three-dimensional neutrosophical vector space ‘partial of the neutrosophical vector space $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$.

Let's now note that:

$$\forall A, B \in \varepsilon(I): \overrightarrow{AB} \in E(I) \Leftrightarrow T(\overrightarrow{AB}) = 0$$

Thus, if $\overrightarrow{AB} \in E(I)$ ‘then A, B are two simultaneous events.

2.3. C. Neutrosophical peaceful ancestors:

The final element of the neutrosophic Galilean structure is the scalar neutrosophic product defined on the neutrosophic simultaneous space (.), which makes the three-dimensional neutrosophic simultaneous space an Euclidean neutrosophic one.

If A and B are two simultaneous events ‘then the vector $\overrightarrow{AB}$ is an simultaneous vector² and therefore has a norm:

$$\|\overrightarrow{AB}\| = \sqrt{\overrightarrow{AB} \cdot \overrightarrow{AB}} = \sqrt{AB^2}$$

we call here then non-negative neutrosophic number $\|\overrightarrow{AB}\|$, the neutrosophic distance between the two simultaneous events A and B .

If A, B, C three events are simultaneous ‘and event A is different from events B and C ‘then we define a fundamental angle that is not directed : $\theta = \widehat{BAC}$. its value is given by:

$$\theta = \frac{\overrightarrow{AB} \cdot \overrightarrow{AC}}{\|\overrightarrow{AB}\| \|\overrightarrow{AC}\|}$$

In fact ‘it is not possible to talk about distances and angles when events are not simultaneous ‘for example ‘we can talk about the distance between Paris and London now ‘but we cannot talk about the distance between Pares now and London tomorrow. Such questions have relative answers in material frames.

2.4. The event coordinate frames according to neutrosophic logic:

¹ We note that event A alone does not have a neutrosophical time ‘time needs two events ‘which is the passed time between these two events

² From the neutrosophic simultaneous space $E(I)$.

Let O be some event from the neutrosophic Galilean event space $\varepsilon(I)$, and let us have $e = (\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3, \vec{e}_4)$ as an argument base of the neutrosophic real vector space $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$.

We call the couple (O, e) an event coordinate frame in the neutrosophic Galilean event space $\varepsilon(I)$.

If A is an arbitrary event from $\varepsilon(I)$, then $\vec{OA} \in \mathbb{R}^4(I)$, thus written as:

$$\vec{OA} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3 + x_4\vec{e}_4 ; x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 \in \mathbb{R}(I)$$

The numbers x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 called the coordinates of the neutrosophic Galilean event A in the frame (O, e) .

Of course ‘changing the point O or the base e , changes the coordinates of the event A . We can never talk here about the regularity or rectangularity of the e base vectors, because there is no neutrosophic scalar product within the neutrosophic Galilean structure on $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$.

2.5. The regular event frame according to the neutrosophical logic:

Let (O, e) event frame in the neutrosophic Galilean space $\varepsilon(I)$. We say that this frame is regular if and only if the following two conditions are met:

a) – vectors $\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3$ are orthonormal simultaneous vectors ‘i.e.:

$$T(\vec{e}_1) = T(\vec{e}_2) = T(\vec{e}_3) = 0 ,$$

$$\vec{e}_i \cdot \vec{e}_j = s_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & ; i = j \\ 0 & ; i \neq j \end{cases}$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, 3$

b) – **Vector** $\vec{e}_4$ **Time-regular**, that is:

$$T(\vec{e}_4) = 1$$

Definition :Let A an arbitrary neutrosophic Galilean event of $\varepsilon(I)$, then the vector $\vec{OA}$ written in a single way in the form:

$$\vec{OA} = x_A\vec{e}_1 + y_A\vec{e}_2 + z_A\vec{e}_3 + t_A\vec{e}_4 ; x_A, y_A, z_A, t_A \in \mathbb{R}(I)$$

We call the neutrosophic coordinates x_A, y_A, z_A the spatial coordinates of event A and neutrosophical coordinate t_A time coordinate of event A ‘which represents the passed time from event O to event A .

Let's note **that**

$$T(\vec{OA}) = x_A T(\vec{e}_1) + y_A T(\vec{e}_2) + z_A T(\vec{e}_3) + t_A T(\vec{e}_4) = x_A \times 0 + y_A \times 0 + z_A \times 0 + t_A \times 1 = t_A$$

If B is another neutrosophic Galilean event ‘we write:

$$\vec{OB} = x_B\vec{e}_1 + y_B\vec{e}_2 + z_B\vec{e}_3 + t_B\vec{e}_4$$

and from it

$$\vec{AB} = \vec{OB} - \vec{OA}$$

Consequently

$$T(\vec{AB}) = T(\vec{OB}) - T(\vec{OA}) = t_B - t_A$$

That is ‘the passing time from event A to event B is : $t_B - t_A$.

Definition: Suppose that the neutrosophical Galilee events A and B are non-simultaneous ‘i.e $t_B \neq t_A$, but the spatial coordinates are identical ‘that is:

$$x_A = x_B, y_A = y_B, z_A = z_B$$

In this case ‘we say that the two neutrosophic Galilean events A and B are occurring in the same place in the frame (O, e) , but at different times.

Let's note that the occurrence of events A and B in the same place in the frame (O, e) means that:

$$\vec{AB} = (t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_4$$

So, the writing $\vec{AB}$ in this form ‘it is a necessary and sufficient condition to occur in the same place in the frame (O, e) .

In fact ‘the occurrence of the two events in the same place does not have an absolute meaning but is related to the event coordinate frame.

To illustrate this fact suppose that (α, β, γ) is a triple of $\mathbb{R}(I)$ different from the triple $(0,0,0)$ and let's put:

$$\vec{e}_4 = \alpha\vec{e}_1 + \beta\vec{e}_2 + \gamma\vec{e}_3 + \vec{e}_4$$

Note that:

$$T(\vec{e}_4) = T(\vec{e}_4) = 1$$

That is the vector $\vec{e}_4$ time-regular.

Therefore, the frame $(O, \acute{e})$ where $\acute{e} \equiv (\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3, \vec{e}_4)$ also an regular frame for the neutrosophic Galilean space $\varepsilon(I)$, however:

$$\begin{aligned} \overrightarrow{AB} &= (t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_4 = \\ &= -\alpha(t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_1 - \beta(t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_2 - \gamma(t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_3 + (t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_4 \neq (t_B - t_A)\vec{e}_4 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the events A and B do not occur in the same place in the frame $(O, \acute{e})$, although they are in the same place in the frame (O, e) .

2.6. Spatial frames:

Let A_t a continuous³ set of neutrosophic Galilean events has a single element in each moment. We call this group a spatial point. The best representation of a spatial point is the material point. The set of positions occupied by the material point is continuous, it does not disappear and appear, and it does not have two positions at the same neutrosophic moment. When there is no confusion, we refer to the set A_t with the symbol A only, and We'll also symbolize the event that the set represents at each moment with the symbol A as well.

Let O be a spatial point, and t is a neutrosophic real parameter representing the neutrosophic time related to an event Q , in such a way that the time of an event A is $T(\overrightarrow{QA}) = t$, and let also $[\vec{e}_1(t), \vec{e}_2(t), \vec{e}_3(t)]$ a base of the spatial space E , related to the neutrosophic parameter t .

We call the set $[O, \vec{e}_1(t), \vec{e}_2(t), \vec{e}_3(t)]$ consisting of the spatial point O at the moment t and the base $[\vec{e}_1(t), \vec{e}_2(t), \vec{e}_3(t)]$ spatial frame.

Let P be a spatial point of the neutrosophic Galilean space $\varepsilon(I)$, then the vector $\overrightarrow{OP}$ belongs at each moment to the spatial space E , and therefore written at each moment in a single form as follows:

$$\overrightarrow{OP} = x(t)\vec{e}_1(t) + y(t)\vec{e}_2(t) + z(t)\vec{e}_3(t)$$

Functions

$$x = x(t), y = y(t), z = z(t); t = t_1 + It_2 \in \mathbb{R}(I)$$

represents the movement of the point P in the frame $(O, \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3)$.

2.7. Inertial frames:

Let $(O, \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3, \vec{e}_4)$ an neutrosophic regular event frame in the neutrosophic Galilean space $\varepsilon(I)$, let us define a spatial point D as the set:

$$\{D(t); \overrightarrow{OD}(t) = t\vec{e}_4; t \in \mathbb{R}(I)\}$$

We call the neutrosophic spatial frame $(D, \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3)$ an inertial frame, and if P is neutrosophic spatial point, then the vector $\overrightarrow{OP}$ be a spatial vector, written in a single way:

$$\overrightarrow{OP} = x_1\vec{e}_1 + x_2\vec{e}_2 + x_3\vec{e}_3$$

And here we call (x, y, z, t) the coordinates of event P , where t indicates the moment of the event and (x, y, z) to the spatial coordinates of the event.

2.8. The neutrosophic Galilean transformations:

Let us have the two neutrosophical event frames $(O, \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3, \vec{e}_4)$ and $(Q, \vec{\varepsilon}_1, \vec{\varepsilon}_2, \vec{\varepsilon}_3, \vec{\varepsilon}_4)$, let P be an event from the neutrosophic Galilean events space $\varepsilon(I)$, and suppose the neutrosophical coordinates of this event in the frame $(O, \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3, \vec{e}_4)$ are (x, y, z, t) , but the neutrosophical coordinates of this event P in the second frame $(Q, \vec{\varepsilon}_1, \vec{\varepsilon}_2, \vec{\varepsilon}_3, \vec{\varepsilon}_4)$, are (X, Y, Z, T) .

Definition: We call the relations that give us the neutrosophical coordinates (x, y, z, t) in terms of the neutrosophical coordinates (X, Y, Z, T) a neutrosophic Galilean transformations, which are:

1) - Translation:

³ The neutrosophic geometry of $\varepsilon(I)$ is the same affine geometry with $\mathbb{R}^4(I)$.

Let's suppose that: $\vec{\varepsilon}_1 = \vec{e}_1, \vec{\varepsilon}_2 = \vec{e}_2, \vec{\varepsilon}_3 = \vec{e}_3, \vec{\varepsilon}_4 = \vec{e}_4$, and let's put

$$\vec{OQ} = \alpha\vec{e}_1 + \beta\vec{e}_2 + \gamma\vec{e}_3 + \tau\vec{e}_4$$

where $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \tau)$ are the neutrosophical event coordinates of event Q in the neutrosophical event frame $(O, \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3, \vec{e}_4)$. For an arbitrary neutrosophical event P from the neutrosophical Galilean events space $\varepsilon(I)$, we can write:

$$\vec{OP} = x\vec{e}_1 + y\vec{e}_2 + z\vec{e}_3 + t\vec{e}_4$$

$$\vec{QP} = X\vec{e}_1 + Y\vec{e}_2 + Z\vec{e}_3 + T\vec{e}_4$$

but $\vec{OP} = \vec{OQ} + \vec{QP}$, consequently:

$$(x - \alpha - X)\vec{e}_1 + (y - \beta - Y)\vec{e}_2 + (z - \gamma - Z)\vec{e}_3 + (t - \tau - T)\vec{e}_4 = \vec{0}$$

And we get the transformation:

$$x = \alpha + X$$

$$y = \beta + Y$$

$$z = \gamma + Z$$

$$t = \tau + T$$

This transformation is called the neutrosophical translation transformation 'in which (α, β, γ) is represented by the spatial part of this translation 'and τ is the spatial part of this translation.

II) – The neutrosophical Spatial rotation:

Suppose that $Q = O$ and $\vec{\varepsilon}_4 = \vec{e}_4$, and let P be an arbitrary neutrosophical Galilean event from $\varepsilon(I)$, then:

$$\vec{OP} = x\vec{e}_1 + y\vec{e}_2 + z\vec{e}_3 + t\vec{e}_4$$

$$\vec{QP} = X\vec{e}_1 + Y\vec{e}_2 + Z\vec{e}_3 + T\vec{e}_4$$

This can only be achieved if:

$$x\vec{e}_1 + y\vec{e}_2 + z\vec{e}_3 = X\vec{e}_1 + Y\vec{e}_2 + Z\vec{e}_3$$

And

$$t = T$$

Thus 'there exist a neutrosophical rotation matrix $A(I)$, that satisfies the following:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = A(I) \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix}$$

$$t = T$$

This transformation is called neutrosophical rotation in the neutrosophical spatial space 'the neutrosophical matrix $A(I)$ is determined by three neutrosophical real parameters (the neutrosophical Euler angles).

III) – The neutrosophical uniform straight-line motion :

Suppose that:

$$Q = O$$

and

$$\vec{\varepsilon}_1 = \vec{e}_1, \vec{\varepsilon}_2 = \vec{e}_2, \vec{\varepsilon}_3 = \vec{e}_3$$

Let's put:

$$\vec{\varepsilon}_4 = a\vec{e}_1 + b\vec{e}_2 + c\vec{e}_3 + \vec{e}_4$$

Let P be an arbitrary Galilean neutrosophical event from the neutrosophical Galilean event space $\varepsilon(I)$, then:

$$\vec{OP} = x\vec{e}_1 + y\vec{e}_2 + z\vec{e}_3 + t\vec{e}_4$$

$$\vec{OP} = X\vec{e}_1 + Y\vec{e}_2 + Z\vec{e}_3 + t\vec{e}_4 = (X + at)\vec{e}_1 + (Y + bt)\vec{e}_2 + (Z + ct)\vec{e}_3 + t\vec{e}_4$$

By matching, we find:

$$x = X + at$$

$$y = Y + bt$$

$$z = Z + ct$$

The neutrosophical mechanical interpretation of these relations is that the **second** frame moves relative to the first frame by a neutrosophic uniform straight- line motion, and its neutrosophic velocity vector is

$$\vec{v} = a\vec{e}_1 + b\vec{e}_2 + c\vec{e}_3$$

This transformation is called the neutrosophic transformation of neutrosophic uniform straight-line motion.

3. Conclusions (authors also should add some future directions points related to her/his research)

I) In paper we paper is to provide a new geometrical definition of the inertial frames based on the Galilean Space-Time concept, from the view of the neutrosophic logic.

Remark 1: Translating the origin of the neutrosophic inertial frame (or changing the **neutrosophic time origin** for it (or rotating its neutrosophic spatial base or moving the neutrosophic inertial frames relative to each other in a neutrosophic uniform straight-line movement (change us from one neutrosophic inertial frame to another neutrosophic inertial frame.

Remark 2: In fact, any neutrosophic inertial transformation is a combination of these transformations and therefore an element of 10 - dimensional neutrosophic group called the neutrosophic Galilean transformations group.

II) **Suggestions:** The results of this paper are the first step to discuss the neutrosophic inertial frames in:

- Relativity mechanics.
- Quantum mechanics.

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